

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

MBK- $T_{1/2}$ -SPACES

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ABSTRACT

Firstly, we give some characterizations of the concepts both mbk-closed sets and mbk-g-closed sets. Then, we obtain that mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space is stronger than mbk- T_0 -space and weaker than mbk- T_1 -space. To give a decomposition of mbk- T_1 -space, we define the concept of mbk-symmetric as a new space and give a characterization of this space. Finally, we also obtain that each of the mbk- T_i -space such that $i = \{0, 1/2, 1\}$ concepts coincides with the other in mbk-symmetric spaces.

Keywords: mbk-open sets, mbk-closed sets, mbk-g-closed sets, mbk- T_i -spaces ($i = \{0, 1/2, 1\}$), mbk-symmetric spaces.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

Topology is a new branch of geometry. Each of elements of a topology is called open set. On the other hand; the concept of δ -open sets was introduced by Velicko [10] as a strong type of the concept of open sets. Then, some of modifications of this type of set have been densely studied from authors such as [8], [1], [2], [3], [4] and [7]. In fact, the purpose of this study is to introduce mbk-open sets. Topology is a special subcollection of $P(Z)$ such that $P(Z)$ is power set of Z . We use the symbol (Z, τ) for a topological space. For a $T \subseteq Z$, the closure of T and the interior of T are denoted by $cl(T)$ and $int(T)$, respectively in a space (Z, τ) . It is known that a subset T is said to be regular open (resp. regular closed) [9] if $T = int(cl(T))$ (resp. $T = cl(int(T))$). The δ -interior of T [10] is consist of $M \subseteq T$ such that for every M is regular open and is denoted by $\delta int(T)$ and defined. A subset X is called δ -open if $T = \delta int(T)$. The collection of all δ -open sets is a topology on Z and denoted by τ^δ such that $\tau^\delta \subseteq \tau$. The complement of a δ -open is called δ -closed. Similarly, the δ -closure of T [9] is consist of $z \in Z$ such that $(K \cap P) \neq \emptyset$ for every K is regular closed neighborhood of $z \in Z$ and is denoted by $\delta cl(T)$. A subset T is said to be generalized closed set [6] if $cl(T) \subseteq U$, whenever $T \subseteq U$ and U is open. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space and $X \subseteq Z$. Then X is said to be a mbk-open [5] if $X \subseteq [cl(\delta int(X)) \cup int(cl(int(X)))]$.

2. MBK-G-CLOSED SETS AND MBK- $T_{1/2}$ -SPACES

We must state that this section is consisted of two parts. In the first part, we introduce the notions of mbk-closed sets and mbk-g-closed set in topological spaces and obtain some characterizations and properties. In the last part, we give that some fundamental and important properties of mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space.

Definition 2.1. Let X be a subset of a topological space (Z, τ) . X is said to be an mbk-closed if its complement is a mbk-open.

The intersection of all mbk-closed sets containing X is said to be mbk-closure of X and it is denoted by $mbk-cl(X)$. Of course, the next property is true: " X is mbk-closed set in (Z, τ) if and only if $X = mbk-cl(X)$."

Theorem 2.2. For the mbk-closure of subsets X, Y in a topological space (Z, τ) , the next properties hold:

- (1) If $X \subseteq Y$, then $mbk-cl(X) \subseteq mbk-cl(Y)$;
- (2) $mbk-cl(X)$ is an mbk-closed, that is $mbk-cl(X) = mbk-cl(mbk-cl(X))$;
- (3) $z \in mbk-cl(X)$ if and only if $X \cap T \neq \emptyset$ for every mbk-open set T of Z containing z .

Proof. It is obvious.

Since g-closed set is a generalization of closed sets. So, we define a type of generalized closed set using mbk-closed.

Definiton 2.3. A subset of X of a topological space (Z, τ) is said to be mbk-g-closed if $mbk-cl(X) \subseteq T$ whenever $X \subseteq T$ and T is a mbk-open set in Z .

Proposition 2.4. In a topological space (Z, τ) , $X \subseteq Z$ is mbk-g-closed if and only if $mbk-cl(\{z\}) \cap T \neq \emptyset$ holds for every $z \in mbk-cl(X)$.

Proof. Sufficiency. Let T be a mbk-open set and $X \subseteq T$. According to hypothesis, there exists a $y \in mbk-cl(\{z\})$ and $y \in X \subseteq T$. It follows from Theorem 2.2(3) that $T \cap \{z\} \neq \emptyset$. Therefore $z \in T$ and this implies that $mbk-cl(X) \subseteq T$. So, X is a mbk-g-closed in (Z, τ) .

Necessity. Let X be a mbk-g-closed subset of Z and $z \in mbk-cl(X)$ such that $mbk-cl(\{z\}) \cap T \neq \emptyset$. According to Theorem 2.2(2) since $mbk-cl(\{z\})$ is a mbk-closed, we have $(Z - (mbk-cl(\{z\})))$ is a mbk-open set from Definition 1.1. Since $X \subseteq (Z - (mbk-cl(\{z\})))$ and X is a mbk-g-closed, we have $mbk-cl(X) \subseteq (Z - (mbk-cl(\{z\})))$ and hence $z \notin mbk-cl(X)$. This is contradiction and hence $mbk-cl(\{z\}) \cap X \neq \emptyset$.

Theorem 2.5. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space and $X \subseteq Z$. If $mbk-cl(\{z\}) \cap X \neq \emptyset$ holds for every $z \in mbk-cl(X)$, then $(mbk-cl(X) - X)$ doesn't contain a non-empty mbk-closed set.

Proof. Let K is a non-empty mbk-closed set and $K \subseteq (mbk-cl(X) - X)$. If $z \in K$, then we have $z \in mbk-cl(X)$. So, $\emptyset \neq (mbk-cl(\{z\}) \cap X) \subseteq (mbk-cl(K) \cap X) = K \cap X$ and so $K \cap X \neq \emptyset$. This is a contradiction.

Corollary 2.6. For a subset X of a topological space (Z, τ) , the next equivalent is hold: " X is an mbk-g-closed set if and only if $X = (K - F)$, where K is an mbk-closed and F contains no non-empty mbk-closed subset."

Proof. Necessity. The proof is obtained from Proposition 2.4 and Theorem 2.5 by taking $K = \text{mbk-cl}(X)$ and $F = (\text{mbk-cl}(X) - X)$.

Sufficiency. If $X = (K - F)$ and $X \subseteq T$ with T is a mbk-open, then $(K \cap (Z - T))$ is a mbk-closed subset of F and hence it is empty. Therefore, $\text{mbk-cl}(X) \subseteq K \subseteq T$.

Theorem 2.7. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space. If $X \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-g-closed set and $X \subseteq Y \subseteq \text{mbk-cl}(X)$, then $Y \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-g-closed.

Proof. Let X be an mbk-g-closed set such that $X \subseteq Y \subseteq \text{mbk-cl}(X)$. Let T be a mbk-open set of Z such that $Y \subseteq T$. Since X is a mbk-g-closed, we have $\text{mbk-cl}(X) \subseteq T$. Using Theorem 2.2(1) and Theorem 2.2(2), $\text{mbk-cl}(X) \subseteq \text{mbk-cl}(Y) \subseteq \text{mbk-cl}(\text{mbk-cl}(X)) = \text{mbk-cl}(X) \subseteq T$ and hence $\text{mbk-cl}(Y) \subseteq T$. So, $T \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-open and $Y \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-g-closed.

Theorem 2.8. Let (Z, τ) be a topological space. Then for each $z \in Z$, either $\{z\} \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-closed or $(Z - \{z\}) \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-g-closed.

Proof. Assume that $\{z\}$ isn't mbk-closed, then $(Z - \{z\})$ isn't mbk-open from Definition 2.1. Let T be any mbk-open set such that $(Z - \{z\}) \subseteq T$ and hence $T = Z$. Therefore $\text{mbk-cl}(Z - \{z\}) \subseteq T$ and hence $(Z - \{z\})$ is a mbk-g-closed.

Definition 2.9. A topological space (Z, τ) is said to be mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space if every mbk-g-closed set is mbk-closed.

Theorem 2.10. A topological space (Z, τ) is a mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space if and only if $\{z\} \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-closed or mbk-open.

Proof. Necessity. Assume that $\{z\} \subseteq Z$ isn't mbk-closed. From Theorem 2.8, $(Z - \{z\})$ is a mbk-g-closed and using hypothesis we have $(Z - \{z\})$ is a mbk-g-closed and hence $\{z\} \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-open.

Sufficiency. Let K be a mbk-g-closed subset of Z and $z \in \text{mbk-cl}(K)$. Then, $\{z\}$ is a mbk-closed or mbk-open.

(1) Assume that $\{z\}$ is a mbk-closed and $z \notin K$. Then, we have $z \in (\text{mbk-cl}(K) - K)$. But according to Theorem 2.3, this isn't possible and hence we have $z \in K$. So $\text{mbk-cl}(K) = K$ and hence K is mbk-closed.

(2) Assume that $\{z\}$ is a mbk-open. By using Theorem 2.2(3), we have $\{z\} \cap K \neq \emptyset$ and hence $z \in K$. This implies that $\text{mbk-cl}(K) \subseteq K$ and hence K is a mbk-closed.

Eventually, we obtain that (Z, τ) is a mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space from Definition 2.9.

Definition 2.11. A topological space (Z, τ) is called a mbk-symmetric space if for z and y in Z , $z \in \text{mbk-cl}(\{y\})$ implies that $y \in \text{mbk-cl}(\{z\})$.

Theorem 2.12. (Z, τ) is a mbk-symmetric space if and only if $\{z\} \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-g-closed, for each $z \in Z$.

Proof. Necessity. Let $\{z\} \subseteq T$, $T \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-open and $\text{mbk-cl}(\{z\}) \not\subseteq T$. So, $[\text{mbk-cl}(\{z\}) \cap (Z - T)] \neq \emptyset$ is true. There is $y \in [\text{mbk-cl}(\{z\}) \cap (Z - T)]$ and using Definition 2.11, $z \in \text{mbk-cl}(\{y\})$ is obtained. Since $y \in (Z - T)$ and $(Z - T) \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-closed, $\text{mbk-cl}(\{y\}) \subseteq (Z - T)$ from Theorem 2.2(2). So, $z \in \text{mbk-cl}(\{y\}) \subseteq (Z - T)$ and $z \notin T$. This is contradiction and hence, $\{z\}$ is a mbk-g-closed for each $z \in Z$.

Sufficiency. Let $\{z\}$ is a mbk-g-closed, for each $z \in Z$. Let $z \in \text{mbk-cl}(\{y\})$ and $y \notin \text{mbk-cl}(\{z\})$. Then, $\{y\} \subseteq (Z - \text{mbk-cl}(\{z\}))$ and $\text{mbk-cl}(\{y\}) \subseteq (Z - \text{mbk-cl}(\{z\}))$. So $z \in (Z - \text{mbk-cl}(\{y\}))$. This is a contradiction and we have $y \in \text{mbk-cl}(\{z\})$. This shows that (Z, τ) is a mbk-symmetric.

Definition 2.13. A topological space (Z, τ) is said to be

(1) mbk- T_0 -space if for each pair of distinct points z, y in Z there exists a mbk-open set T such that either $z \in T$ and $y \notin T$ or $y \in T$ and $z \notin T$.

(2) mbk- T_1 -space if for each pair of distinct points z, y in Z there exist two mbk-open sets T and U such that either $z \in T$ and $y \notin T$ and $y \in U$ and $z \notin U$.

Lemma 2.14. A topological space (z, τ) is an mbk- T_1 -space if and only if the singletons are mbk-closed sets.

Lemma 2.15. Every mbk- T_1 -space is a mbk- T_0 .

Corollary 2.16. Every mbk- T_1 -space is a mbk-symmetric.

Proof. Let (Z, τ) is a mbk- T_1 -space. Using Lemma 2.14, every singleton is a mbk-g-closed subset of Z . Hence we obtained that (Z, τ) is a mbk-symmetric space from Theorem 2.12.

Corollary 2.17. A topological space (Z, τ) is a mbk- T_1 if and only if it is a mbk-symmetric and mbk- T_0 .

Proof. Necessity. The proof is obtained from Corollary 2.16 and Lemma 2.15.

Sufficiency. Let $y \neq z$ and (Z, τ) be a mbk- T_0 -space. Assume that $z \in T \subseteq (Z - \{y\})$ for some $T \subseteq Z$ is a mbk-open. So, $z \notin \text{mbk-cl}(\{y\})$ and hence $y \notin \text{mbk-cl}(\{z\})$. Then, there exists a mbk-open set U such that $y \in U \subseteq (Z - \{z\})$. This shows that (Z, τ) be a mbk- T_1 -space.

Remark 2.18. For any topological space (Z, τ) , the next statements are hold:

(1) If (Z, τ) is a mbk- T_1 -space, then it is a mbk- $T_{1/2}$.

(2) If (Z, τ) is a mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space, then it is a mbk- T_0 .

Proposition 2.19. For a mbk-symmetric space (Z, τ) , the next properties are equivalent:

(1) (Z, τ) is a mbk- T_0 -space.

(2) (Z, τ) is a mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -space.

(3) (Z, τ) is a mbk- T_1 -space.

Proof. (1) \Leftrightarrow (3). The proof is obvious from that Corollary 2.11.

(3) \Rightarrow (2) and (2) \Rightarrow (1) are obtained directly from Remark 2.13.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The notion of generalized closed sets is an important subject on topological spaces. To contribute of this area, we have devoted this article to investigating a new generalization of closed sets which name is mbk-closed. We give a characterization of mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -spaces which is related to an mbk-closed set or mbk-open set. To obtain decomposition of mbk- T_1 -spaces, we introduce the concept of mbk-symmetric spaces. We obtain that mbk- $T_{1/2}$ -spaces is between mbk- T_0 -spaces and mbk- T_1 -spaces. Finally, in mbk-symmetric spaces we also give that the three separation axioms mentioned above coincide with each other. Our future plan will focus on decompositions of mbk-closed sets related to

mbk-g-closed. Then, we will study on continuity using what we can get.

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